

Renewable Energy Today and Tomorrow

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Abstract: The review paper discusses issues related to transition to renewable energy in order to reduce greenhouse gas emissions. Attention is paid to the conferences of specialists that have recently taken place under the auspices of the UN and in Moscow. Based on conversations with their participants, the problems that arise about this are described. As an illustration of the problems of the "green agenda" is the situation with the automotive industry, which currently produces up to 40% of environmental pollution.

1 INTRODUCTION

From year to year, human activity leads to increasing emission of greenhouse gases - the main cause of global warming. The results of rising global temperatures are melting of polar ice, rising sea levels, droughts and rainstorms, an increase in the size of deserts, and the death of the biosphere. Impacts important to humanity include the threat to food security due to negative impacts on crop yields (especially in Asia and Africa) and the loss of human habitat due to rising sea levels. These problems threaten in the future such countries as Netherlands, Bangladesh, and island states. In 2021, at the 26th UN Climate Change Conference, Tuvalu's foreign minister delivered his video message while standing knee-deep in water. So he showed that his state could disappear due to climate change and rising ocean levels (Polak, 2022).

The world community is making efforts to stabilize the concentration of greenhouse gases in the atmosphere in order to prevent dangerous anthropogenic impact on the climate system. In 1992, the UN Framework Convention on Climate Change was adopted, which was signed by more than 180 countries. The Paris Climate Agreement (2015) sets a long-term goal of keeping the increase in global average temperature at 1.5°C. An important tool for achieving it is the accelerated transition from the combustion of various types of fossil fuels to the widespread use of renewable energy sources (RES).

Renewable energy is energy derived from natural sources that are replenished at a higher rate than they are consumed. Sunlight and wind, for example, are such sources that are constantly being replenished.

2 RENEWABLE ENERGY SOURCES

In February 2023, the new report of the International Energy Agency (IEA) on the electricity market appeared (Electricity Market Report, 2023). It suggests that, after slowing slightly to 2% last year amid the turmoil of the global energy crisis and exceptional weather, global electricity demand growth will accelerate to an average of 3% over the next three years. At the same time, renewable energy sources and nuclear power are growing fast enough to meet almost all of these additional needs. It is expected that in 2025 RES will bypass coal and become the main supplier of electricity on the planet; their share in the global energy balance will increase from 29% in 2022 to 35% in 2025. At the same time, the share of coal, natural gas and nuclear power plants will continue to decline.

"In the next five years, the world will have as much renewable energy as in the last 20 years," said Fatih Birol, head of the IEA. Renewable energy received a boost due to the energy crisis caused by the cessation of oil and gas exports from Russia. As a

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result, the EU countries were forced to accelerate the transition to alternative sources of electricity. This suggests that a tipping point is approaching in terms of emissions in the energy sector. Now it is necessary that low-emission sources can grow even faster. So the world will have a reliable supply of electricity while meeting climate goals.

The IEA report states (p.93-94) that Russia is the largest consumer of electricity in Eurasia with an annual consumption of 1000+ TWh. Electricity consumption in Russia increased by 1.5% (+16 TWh) in 2022. At the same time, in the second half of the year, the decline in industrial and commercial activity slowed down the growth in electricity demand to 0.7% yoy. In the first ten months of 2022, generating capacity in Russia increased by 0.5% compared to the same period last year. Gas-fired generation grew by almost 1 GW, offsetting a 0.3 GW reduction in coal-fired power generation. Nuclear and hydropower capacities remained stable, while solar capacity increased by almost 8% (+0.25 GW). Fossil fuel power generation, including coal, natural gas and oil-fired power plants, increased by 3% compared to 2021 levels and remains at more than 60% of total electricity supply.

2.1 The Conference on Renewable Energy

Renewable energy issues were discussed at the recent conference "The Future of Renewable Energy in Russia", organized by the Vedomosti newspaper. The conferences held by this newspaper for 20 years are well known to the business community. This project was created on the basis of the experience and technologies of the world famous Financial Times publishing house. The conference on renewable energy brought together industry professionals - heads of generating and supply companies, energy consumers, government officials, the banking community, and public organizations.

According to Deputy Minister of Energy P. Snikkars, the share of RES in electricity generation in Russia by 2050 can grow significantly - up to 12.5% of the total generation, while more than 90 GW of capacity will be provided from renewable energy sources. "We have already created a fairly serious complex for the production of equipment for solar and wind generation." As one of the promising areas, Mr. Snikkars noted the introduction of RES in remote and isolated areas of the Far East and the Arctic.

One of the most important topics was the impact of the imposed sanctions on the state of the renewable energy market. After an extremely difficult recovery

period for the entire Russian economy from the Covid-19 pandemic, 2022 has become even more stressful and brought new restrictions and barriers to investment projects. The unprecedented sanctions have also had a major impact on the renewable energy sector. Difficulties also affected national companies that localized the production of equipment for renewable energy generation projects, primarily due to the increase in the cost of investment projects, which was associated with disruption of supply chains and difficulties in attracting capital.

S. Morozov, Chairman of the Association of the Wind Industry: "Due to the disruption of supply chains and complex logistics, the commissioning of a number of Russian wind farms has been delayed. Previously, almost all spare parts came from abroad. Foreign companies that produced wind turbines were interested in profiting from supplies, but they didn't share their competencies to the production of components. Russia made a big mistake by not demanding the transfer of intellectual rights to components in the field of wind energy. Foreign suppliers of wind turbines often located the production of various components in third countries, and not at our enterprises. Having left the Russian market, they left neither the rights to release their products, nor the corresponding technologies. For example, after the departure of the Danish company Vestas, one of the world's largest manufacturers of wind turbines, the production of blades for wind power plants also disappeared in Russia." It should be noted that in December 2022 Enel company received permission to commission the largest wind power plant in Russia, the Kola WPP, with capacity of 201 MW, located beyond the Arctic Circle in the Murmansk region. The equipment of the wind farm is designed taking into account the specifics of operation at extremely low temperatures (Filippova, 2022).

More about the Vedomosti conference. V. Seleznev, Deputy Chairman of the Duma Committee on Energy: "What happened with the departure of foreign companies that participated as investors in the localization of the renewable energy industry in Russia, clearly showed the shortcomings of the model that was included in the program of our state support both wholesale and retail markets. Many companies that participated in this localization announced their exit from the market and did not leave any localized technologies: design documentation, copyrights for know-how, and the possibility of production in their absence." State support was aimed at achieving, in particular, technological sovereignty in promising types of generation. Until recently, Russia's influence

on the global energy market was determined by hydrocarbons, but after some (perhaps, long) time, the share of other technologies will increase in the energy sector through an energy transition. The speaker gave examples of decisions that now look dubious. So, NovaWind (a subsidiary of Rosatom) and Hevel are building a plant for the production of equipment for solar energy in Kaliningrad. This region was chosen for investment when exports were focused on Europe. Now, when all logistics chains are being rebuilt to the East, it is hardly worth continuing the development of this plant. In Kalmykia, 300 MW of renewable energy capacities have been built, while there is no such demand there. It was a rash decision, millions of rubles wasted in vain. And further: "We have a big problem with gas turbines. We now have 26 GW of gas turbines at risk of wear. Accordingly, they must be saved so that they do not wear out before the time when we will have our own turbines or restore logistics chains for the supply of those turbines that we cannot bring now. And we have a failure in the production of certain types of turbines until at least 2028. We have no understanding of where to get components, materials, software, and at the same time there is no indexing. But in 2021, prices were very different from those that are now, and from those that await us. Prices for materials and components increased by 20-112%. At the same time, Mr. Seleznev noted a very large safety margin of the Russian energy system. "It is redundant – and this is right and good. The second plus is that it is centralized. I think that we will cope with the challenges and threats that are now facing us."

Director of Association for the Development of Renewable Energy A. Zhikharev noted that renewable energy technologies are actively developing, and their price is decreasing. So, over the past decade, the cost of solar panels has decreased 10 times; technologies for wind energy are getting cheaper a little slower, but also significantly. He recalled: "More than 150 GW of renewable energy capacities are commissioned annually in the world. In some countries, for example, in China, more than 100 GW per year, in Europe - about 45–50 GW. And, of course, the Russian 1 GW per year is a very small number. At the same time, this is a serious step forward for the domestic energy sector, because until 2015 renewable energy projects could be counted on the fingers. By 2035, solar and wind generation facilities with a total capacity of 8.5 GW are expected to be commissioned." According to him, "the use of renewable energy sources is economically justified. That is, one kilowatt-hour of electricity produced on the basis of wind or solar, depending on the location

of the generation facility, can cost several times cheaper than a kilowatt-hour produced by a gas, coal or nuclear power plant. And economic efficiency begins to play a major role in the development of RES... Experts say that it is impossible to achieve a 100% share of energy from RES in the energy system. We are not talking about 100% right now. However, I am absolutely sure that in combination with new solutions and technologies (hydrogen energy, lithium-ion, mechanical or flow storage devices, etc.), this direction will actively develop." In modern Russia, renewable energy sources can become the main source of electricity for remote small settlements. In conjunction with traditional generation, they become one of the most profitable sources of energy in distributed energy in remote and isolated areas.

It was noted at the conference that most of the diesel generation facilities in hard-to-reach areas have a high cost of electricity generation from 35 to 270 rubles / kWh, which is due to high costs for the delivery and storage of diesel fuel, as well as wear of generating equipment. RusHydro's "green" projects are aimed at supplying energy to small settlements in the North and the Far East (there are 143 such settlements only in Yakutia); this requires new approaches. The company is replacing part of the diesel generation with renewable energy. In the near future, it is planned to build hybrid diesel-solar installations in 72 villages of Yakutia (total capacity of 93 MW, of which 22 MW are solar power plants) and 7 settlements of Kamchatka with a total of 30 MW, of which 7 MW is the capacity of wind farms and solar power plants. The implementation of plans is hindered by the fact that the industry is not interested in low-power "windmills" for small settlements with a capacity of 300-500 W, especially for the north in the Arctic version. There are not enough domestic components for solar power plants.

The energy transition is a complex technological, economic and social task that should be solved smoothly and gradually, attempts at an "aggressive energy transition" threaten both the economy and the livelihoods of the population of our country. Most coal-fired power plants in Siberia and the Far East also supply heat to citizens, so replacing coal with renewable energy sources that do not produce heat is impossible in these regions. In Siberia, many stations are built directly on coal mines, and it is not economically feasible to transport gas hundreds of kilometers to them. There is also an important social aspect of the problem of abandoning coal: the coal industry is an employer for 160 thousand people, and taking into account adjacent areas up to 1.3 million

people. Coal plants play an important social role, that is S (social in terms of ESG), especially in such regions as Kuzbass or Vorkuta. The point of view was expressed that the energy transition in Russia should begin not with renewable energy, but with social policy. We need to start with supporting the low-income population in certain regions during the energy transition. In this area, the approach is to be transformed: from providing assistance to certain categories of citizens and social groups (women, children, pensioners) to individual support for those who actually receive low incomes. We need differentiation of tariffs for the population.

2.2 Problems and Difficulties of RES

It is necessary to keep in mind the side effects of "green" technologies. One of the problems is the wear and tear of the first generation of wind turbines. Utilization of wind turbines has a completely non-environmental side. Their blades are made of composite materials consisting of carbon fiber, fiberglass, balsa wood, polyurethane, alloy and epoxy. They are not intended for recycling. The length of the wind blade is about 40 meters (larger than a Boeing wing), it weighs seven tons, and they cannot just be thrown away. The blades are sawn and buried in the ground. The volume of waste amounts to millions of tons, the organization of huge landfills for their disposal violates the ecological balance, turning green areas into wastelands. Another example is associated with the extraction of lithium, which is necessary for the creation of batteries for cars and smart phones. Chile has 29% of the world's lithium reserves, and huge evaporation ponds are visible even from space in the Atacama Desert. The increase in production destroys the ecosystem, the process of desertification is aggravated: there is an acute shortage of drinking water, a reduction in pastures and crops, and the disappearance of flora and fauna.

In addition to lithium, a large amount of minerals and metals is required for the manufacture of not only solar panels and wind turbines, but also industrial equipment that does not run on carbon fuels, but on electricity. There is already a growing shortage of some raw materials: according to the World Economic Forum, the average cost of copper production has increased by more than 300% in recent years; steel prices are growing as well. There is not even enough sand: for the production of concrete for the installation of windmills or silicone (necessary in the production of solar panels), only sand of a certain quality is suitable. Every year, sand becomes the most sought after raw material (other

than water) and is considered by some to be a key sustainability issue for the 21st century. As deposits are depleted, sand is becoming a factor in geopolitical tensions: for example, China recently imposed a sand embargo on Taiwan to interfere with the production of semiconductor devices.

R. Heinberg from the Institute for Post-Carbon Economics points out that climate change in itself makes it difficult to combat climate change by hindering the energy transition (Heinberg, 2022). The latest striking example is the heat wave of 2022. In China, a drought-driven energy crisis has forced a major battery maker to close factories in Sichuan province. Deliveries of parts needed for the production of Tesla and Toyota have been suspended. In Germany, the water level in the Rhine dropped so much that it affected European trade, cutting off the supply of diesel fuel and coal and jeopardizing the operation of both hydro and nuclear power plants. In the past, droughts, which are becoming more frequent and severe, have created problems for hydroelectric power plants in several US states. French nuclear power plants were transferred to a reduced regime, for the cooling of which water from the Rhone is used. French nuclear power generation fell by almost 50% in the summer of 2022, with similar drought- and heat-driven outages occurring in 2018 and 2019. In 2019, severe flooding in southern and western Africa damaged two large hydroelectric power plants in Malawi, leaving large parts of the country without electricity for several days. Extreme conditions threaten the operation of wind turbines and solar panels. On cold, cloudy and windless days, regions that rely heavily on renewable energy experience problems. Storms can damage solar panels, and high temperatures reduce their efficiency. Hurricanes and storms damage offshore wind farms. The energy transition is not easy.

Any kind of activity leads to the depletion of natural resources and pollution. The use of fossil fuels releases carbon into the atmosphere, leading to climate change. The use of renewable energy sources also leads to resource depletion from the extraction of minerals and metals, and to pollution from the disposal of end-of-life panels, turbines and batteries, as well as various industrial processes. It is possible to radically reduce all risks and minimize climate change with a significant reduction in the consumption of energy and raw materials, but this means a voluntary rejection of economic growth. This option is unacceptable neither for wealthy countries accustomed to high levels of consumption, nor for less affluent countries seeking development. The world's poorest countries are now bearing the brunt of

the effects of climate change driven by developed countries that have become wealthy through carbon-emitting industrial activities. To continue to exploit the lands, mineral resources and labor force of relatively poor states so that a wealthy minority can maintain their usual way of life is unacceptable in modern conditions and does not meet the goals of sustainable development.

International efforts, including through the United Nations Organization, are aimed at solving the problem. In November 2022, Sharm el-Sheikh (Egypt) hosted the annual UN climate change conference COP-27, which brought together more than 35,000 participants from 197 countries - heads of state, ministers, business leaders, representatives of civil society, academia and observers.

The most pressing issue of the conference was compensation for damage caused by the effects of climate change. At the same time, the states that bear the least responsibility for such changes are most vulnerable to climate disasters. Discussions on this topic continued until the last moment, but the delegations managed to reach a final agreement: it was decided to create a fund to cover the damage and losses caused by climate disasters. However, the discussion of the financing mechanism of this fund is postponed for further discussions. Another important event of the conference was the adoption of a master plan to accelerate decarbonization in five key sectors: energy, road transport, steel and hydrogen production, and agriculture (COP-27, 2022).

Serious concern was expressed that the goal of the developed countries to collectively mobilize \$100 billion a year starting in 2020 has not yet been achieved. At the same time, it was strongly recommended to achieve this goal, and multilateral development banks and international financial institutions to increase climate finance.

In his emotional address to the participants, UN Secretary-General A. Guterres called for an end to "the suicidal war with nature, which fuels the climate crisis, leads to the extinction of plant and animal species and destroys ecosystems", to take humanity "from the edge of the climate abyss." He recalled the need to keep global warming within 1.5°C and said that while a fund to cover losses and damages is important, it is unlikely that this measure will be enough if "the climate crisis wipes out one of the small island states from the face of the Earth or transforms an entire African country into the desert" (Delivering for people and the planet, 2022). The fight for climate justice and climate ambition will require large-scale investments. The UN chief proposed a climate solidarity pact and called for an

equitable partnership to transition to green energy to accelerate the phase-out of coal and expand the use of renewable energy.

3 ELECTRIC TRANSPORT

We will consider the problems of the "green" program using the example of the automotive industry, which accounts for up to 40% of environmental pollution (Morzharetto, 2021). Today, no one argues whether it is necessary or not to develop electric transport, both personal and public. Two years ago, the International Energy Agency (IEA) predicted that electric vehicles would not achieve a market share of 10% until 2030. However, this happened much earlier in 2022. Buyers are attracted by the environmental friendliness of this mode of transport, and government subsidies in many countries help support demand.

Although sales of all new cars worldwide in 2022 as a whole fell by about 1% to 80.6 million (due to a difficult macroeconomic situation, high inflation and market uncertainties), according to estimates by analysts LMC Automotive and EV-Volumes.com, published in mid-January 2023, sales of electric vehicles increased by 68% to 7.8 million. Thus, approximately one in ten cars sold (9.67% to be exact) had an electric power plant. In Europe, the share of sales of electric vehicles reached 11%, and in China 19%.

Electric vehicle sales are growing amid falling overall sales. Thus, VW managed to sell 8.3 million vehicles last year, which is 7% lower than in 2021. At the same time, sales of electric vehicles of the concern increased by 26%. A drop in total sales with more than doubling EV sales in 2022 was reported by BMW, Ford and Mercedes-Benz.

The main item of expenditure for the maintenance of "classic" cars is fuel. In the world, 70% of crude oil is used for gasoline and diesel fuel. Some is consumed by generators, but most by cars, ships and trains. In the field of transport in the United States, 70% of the oil produced is used, of which 65% is used for cars, that is, almost half of the total. Soon this will come to an end. Cars with internal combustion engines are expelled from large cities and entire regions, their owners will be taxed, and automakers are ordered to convert production to the production of electric vehicles. At the end of October, the European authorities decided: from 2035, it will not be possible to register a single new car with an internal combustion engine in the EU countries, even if it is part of a hybrid power plant. According to the "Fit for 55" strategy, by 2030 the EU countries should reduce

emissions of harmful gases into the atmosphere by 55% compared to 1990, and by 2050 they should move to full carbon neutrality (Kononchuk, 2022). Similar measures are being taken in the US. New ICE vehicle sales bans will go into effect in California and Oregon, and a 2045 deadline for mid- and heavy-duty vehicles sold in the state in New York (Mironenko, 2022).

The current crisis in the automotive industry in Russia creates the conditions for the introduction of electric cars. The departure of leading foreign manufacturers, the destruction of supply chains, the impossibility of supplying components and the rapid localization of complex production (and an internal combustion engine, on average, consists of 5,000 parts), the need to meet new, more stringent environmental standards - all this destroys the ability to manufacture traditional cars. Organization of the production of electric transport is much easier. For example, the creation and launch of a complete battery plant takes only a few months. The assembly process does not require special qualifications from workers and is easily automated; an electric motor, by and large, consists of only two parts - a rotor and a stator, so assembling an electric car is much cheaper. Maintenance of an electric car on average is 40% of the cost of maintaining a car with an internal combustion engine with equal mileage.

In 2021, the Ministry of Industry and Trade announced its intention to introduce a 25% discount on the purchase of electric vehicles on credit and leasing. The preferential car loan program in Russia has been extended to 2023, Russians will be able to get a 35% discount when buying a domestic electric car, but its size should not exceed 925,000 rubles. Against this background, the growth in sales of electric vehicles is impressive: in the first half of 2022, they were bought one and a half times more than a year earlier.

But not everything is so smooth. The cost of an electric car is about 30-50% higher than a gasoline car of the same class. In all countries where appropriate programs have been adopted, sales are growing as long as there are subsidies for buyers and producers. Without government support, many users would choose a car with an internal combustion engine.

The undeveloped infrastructure of charging stations in Russia was named by 65% of those surveyed by the NAFI (National Financial Research Agency) analytical center as the main brake on the growth in popularity of electric vehicles. Charging speed is another reason for the dissatisfaction of opponents of electric vehicles. Refueling a car on an

internal combustion engine is faster than replenishing the power reserve even on fast EZS.

A complex of problems is associated with batteries. The smallest of them is not enough mileage on a single charge; this claim is relevant for old and budget models (the power reserve of Tesla, Lucid Air, Mercedes-Benz models exceeds 500 km). The energy intensity of lithium-titanate batteries in Moscow electric buses is relatively low - 77 kWh; LIAZ travels up to 59 km on one charge. True, they charge 5 times faster and deliver 10 times more current than other lithium-ion batteries.

Speaking of "clean" electric transport, let's not forget that electricity gets into the batteries, as a rule, from thermal power plants, which are far from being "green". Taking into account losses in power networks, about 25-28% reaches the car from the station (with an average efficiency of 40%). For comparison, the efficiency of a conventional car with an internal combustion engine is about 50%

Batteries use lithium, cobalt, manganese, nickel, neodymium, cadmium, the reserves of which on earth are finite, and mining and production cause irreparable damage to nature and human health. So far, there is no effective procedure for recycling batteries, because even an AA battery pollutes up to 20 square meters of land. The batteries of cars and buses are much larger: for example, the Tesla Model S battery has a weight of 540 kg and dimensions of 210 * 150 * 15 cm, an electric bus has up to 2 tons (Sutyagin, 2020).

New legislation in the European Union, the US and other countries makes electric vehicle suppliers responsible for battery disposal at the end of its life. China, the world's largest user of electric vehicles and batteries, is launching its own recycling schemes. In June 2021, US President D. Biden approved a strategy that includes creating conditions to accelerate the recycling of batteries used in electric vehicles for the reuse of lithium and other metals. Spent batteries that are no longer suitable for powering electric vehicles retain about 70% of their capacity and can serve as high-quality energy storage devices. This opens up many possibilities for their reuse. So, an old battery can be converted into a backup energy source for a private house. It charges at night when electricity is cheaper and is used during peak hours or power outages. In this capacity, the battery removed from the machine can last several years. Renault has batteries to power elevators in Paris, Nissan is introducing old batteries for street lighting, BMW is equipping batteries with fast charging stations, Ajax stadium in Amsterdam is using a 3 MW power plant with a battery from Nissan

Leaf electric vehicles. Recycling plants have been set up in several prefectures in Japan. This country is also among the leaders in theoretical research: Japanese chemist Akira Yoshino received the 2019 Nobel Prize for the development of stable lithium-ion batteries.

Bakhtizina and Bakhtizin (2021), who consider the problem from an economic standpoint, note that about 72% of the growth in global investment in the energy transition in 2020 is associated with the electric transport segment. In 2020, \$139 billion (+28.3% yoy) was allocated to the development of electric transport, of which 85% (+43.9% yoy), was spent on passenger electric vehicles.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The country's low-carbon development strategy states the goal of achieving carbon neutrality with sustainable economic growth in the context of the global energy transition. This implies a significant increase in generation based on renewable energy sources while ensuring the necessary level of localization of equipment production in compliance with environmental safety. The envisaged measures should allow Russia to achieve a balance between anthropogenic emissions of greenhouse gases and their absorption no later than 2060.

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